

Grid Security Review

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Structure of the Presentation

- **Introduction**
- Scope
- Security Challenges and Requirements in Grid Computing
 - Security Challenges
 - Security Requirements
- Grid Security Architectures
 - Table of existing Grid efforts
 - The Open Grid Services Security Architecture
 - Grid Security Infrastructure (GSI)
 - The Legion Security Architecture
 - The GLOBE Security Architecture
 - CRISIS
- Conclusions

Introduction

- A Computational Grid is a collection of heterogeneous computing resources spread across multiple administrative domains, serving the task of providing users with an easy access to these resources

- Definition according to I. Foster and C. Kesselman:
“A Computational Grid is a hardware and software infrastructure that provides dependable, consistent, pervasive and inexpensive access to high-end computational capabilities ”

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Scope of the paper

□ Motivation:

“The conventional approach to security, that of enforcing a single, system-wide policy, cannot be applied to large-scale distributed systems”

□ Objectives:

- To identify basic security needs in Grid environments
- To conduct a review of the existing or proposed Grid security architectures and models
- To track down and analyze the most important and exemplary security architectures
- To evaluate and compare those architectures

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Security Challenges

- **Integration** with existing systems and technologies
- **Interoperability** with different hosting environments
- **Trust relationships** between interacting hosting environments

Security Requirements

- Confidentiality
- Integrity
- Privacy
- Identification
- Authentication
- Single logon
- Authorization
- Delegation
- Assurance
- Autonomy
- Policy exchange
- Firewall traversal
- Secure logging
- Manageability

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Table of existing Grid efforts

Grid effort	Organization - Place
Netsolve	University of Tennessee
Ninf	University of Tokyo
Unicore	Germany
Gridbus	University of Melbourne
Condor-G	University of Wisconsin
MPICH-G	University of Northern Illinois
DataGrid	European Union
Javelin	University of California
JXTA	SUN Microsystems
XtremWeb	University of Paris
Legion	Virginia University
Globe	Amsterdam University
WebOS	Berkley University
Globus	Argonn University

The Open Grid Services Security Architecture

- Parent Grid effort: **OGSA**
- Based on abstraction of security components in a single security model
- Main features
 - Proposes a model that secures Grid Services in general
 - Proposes specific security services built to provide the necessary functionality
 - Still in the phase of specifications

Grid Security Infrastructure (GSI)

- Parent Grid Project: **Globus**
- Based on a Grid security architecture proposed by I. Foster et al. in 1998
- Main features
 - **Identification:** X.509 certificates
 - **Authentication:** TLS protocol for mutual authentication (use of SSL also possible)
 - **Confidentiality:** No encryption by default but it can be supported easily
 - **Delegation:** Through temporary identities called proxies
 - **Single sign-on:** Enabled

The Legion Security Architecture

- Parent Grid project: **Legion**
- Has to deal with objects since Legion is an object-oriented meta-system
- Main features
 - **Identification, Confidentiality, Integrity:** Based on a unique, location-independent, Legion Object Identifier (LOID)
 - **Authentication:** Through the use of credentials
 - **Delegation:** By issuing credentials to objects
 - **Access control:** Decentralized
 - **Manageability:** Guarantees that Legion security policies do not compromise OS security policies

The GLOBE Security Architecture

- Parent Grid system: **GLOBE**
 - Based on Distributed Shared Objects (DSOs)
- Based on public key cryptography and digital certificates
- Main features
 - **Identification:** Based on integration of Object IDs (OIDs) with public keys
 - **Assurance:** Use of Java “sand boxing” technique in combination with code signing
 - **Authentication, Confidentiality, Integrity:** Through the concept of secure method invocation

CRISIS

- Parent Grid system: **WebOS**
- Based on the presence of 3 basic entities, namely, *principals*, *objects* and *reference monitors*
- Main features
 - **Identification, Authentication, Authorization:** Identity certificates (X.509)
 - **Delegation:** Transfer certificates (X.509)
 - Remote nodes (local systems) which have
 - A security manager, and
 - A resource provider
 - Security domains

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Conclusions

(1)

<i>Security Requirement</i>	GSI	Legion	Globe	CRISIS
Confidentiality	High	High	Medium	High
Integrity	High	High	Medium	High
Privacy	High	Medium	Medium	Medium
Identification	High	High	High	High
Authentication	High	High	High	High
Single logon	High	Low	Low	Low
Authorization	Medium	High	High	High
Delegation	Medium	Medium	Medium	High
Assurance	Low	Low	High	Medium
Autonomy	High	High	High	Medium
Policy exchange	Low	Low	Low	Low
Firewall traversal	Low	Low	Low	Low
Secure logging	Low	Low	Low	Low
Manageability	Low	Low	Medium	Medium

Conclusions

(2)

- No security architecture fulfills the entire list of Grid security requirements
 - Not unexpected since the area of “Grid security” is still in early stages
- However, several Grid security requirements are fulfilled through a variety of security mechanisms
 - Encouraging for the success of further research

Conclusions

(3)

- The authors suggest that further research is particularly needed in the following Grid computing areas:
 - Firewall traversal
 - Policy exchange, Security Policies
 - Security management
 - Standardization

Questions – Author Contact Info.

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